

Deep XGBoost: Joint probability estimation using classification models. A case study of pure end-to-end XGBoost and ImageNet

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Abstract

Classical ML involves classification models which have strong statistical justifications, proofs and validations. But, the current state of the art CNNs neither have explainability nor have complete theoretical explanations. Image super-resolution and autoencoder are the examples of joint probability that are being considered. Multiplication instructions of inference are not allowed or discouraged. All data has to fit in the RAM while training. So, smart sampling is used.

Keywords: XGBoost, layers, pseudo-label, autoencoder, generative, joint-probability, image superresolution

1 Introduction

The main premises are these:

- Any input to output mapping is of the form $y = f(x)$ (and this does not have to be differentiable always). So, we should be able to predict the bits of the output if the prediction of complete output is difficult for that pixel or voxel (0D or 1D or 2D or 3D).
- Given that the classical ML does not use backpropagation, more data and more dimensions of the data may be a disadvantage if we use vanilla classical ML. An advantage is that, classical ML does not use backpropagation.
- So, we can use the concept of layers and train hierarchical models so that the receptive field is larger. This should mitigate some of the drawbacks of weak learners and instead, use it as an explainability advantage.

- We have the input and we can resize it as needed (unlike the classification output).

Please note that this research will use random to denote both random and pseudo-random statistics. **Please note that the experiments are in progress and the results will likely be published in peer reviewed version only.**

2 Prior Work

Image Pyramids offer compute at multiple scales of image resolutions without having to resort to interpolation everytime.[3] CNNs have the ability to use layers of activation functions (like ReLU).[4] CNNs do not have any obvious explainability. Classical ML algorithms do not have the concept of backpropagation.[5] For reference, Classical ML algorithms involve supervised algorithms like Linear Regression, Logistic Regression, Naive Bayes and SVM and unsupervised algorithms like K-Means clustering, EM, PCA and ICA.[5] Classical ML may work better if there is less data and lesser number of dimensions. Forward-Forward Algorithm (FFA) relies on the idea of layers and "goodness measure".[6] This is very similar to the proposed idea, but, the proposed idea uses XGBoost only and does not use weight training which makes the proposed idea explainable (among other reasons). Instead of FFA-like contrastive divergence, the proposed idea uses pseudo-labels instead. Instead of a "video of images" needed for FFA, the proposed idea uses CNN-like stride. This reduces the need to train it with a lot of negative samples. Also, FFA introduces sleep which explains why brain may not use exact backpropagation.[6] XGBoost uses threshold only during classification inference and works well even when there is class imbalance.[1] ImageNet data is used for these experiments.[7]

The existing state of the art assumes that inverse exists and that inverse is robust enough to predict even when there is noise in the data (unlike the proposed solution).[8] Deep Forest uses input features multiple times and acknowledges that augmented features will likely be drowned out when the feature vectors are high dimensional (and that they will leave it for future exploration). It also doesn't use kernel and stride exactly like CNN.[9] AutoEncoder by Forest uses backward decoding which may not work for different types of classification models. Also, the backward decoding works like backpropagation which may make explanations more difficult as it is not homogeneous across layers.[10] Multi-layer support vector machines require a choice of kernel and are not exactly explainable.[11] Multi-Layer SVM paper explores both primal and dual formulations and for complicated data, CNN layer-like structure is not shown (which makes it computationally expensive). Class Probability Output Network has the assumption that the classifier output is often uni-modal.[12]

3 Classification

- The premise of the idea is that there are layers of XGBoost models and all models have to predict the class of the image.
- The initial layer would be the conversion of RGB to HSV for images. Then, for each 5x5 patch, the XGBoost model would have to predict the class of the entire image (if the number of classes is small).
- Or else, for each bit or each set of bits of class, an XGBoost model has to be trained.
- Of course there will be a lot of noise in the training data as not all patches will have the object that the class denotes. But, this is exactly why this is being done. This is to create weak learners which can help us distinguish between signal and noise.
- If there is a lot of "classification errors", that means that the patches we are talking about have a lot of "noise".

Experiments: Note that these experiments are not complete as of now. But, these are the main ideas:

- The batch training may require a lot of memory and compute. So, for lower layers, simple models are trained while higher layers are trained with complete data and default parameters.
- 256x256 HSV image is used (the complete image is fit into 256x256 and the remaining portion is filled with 0's if the image is not a square image).
- LOC_train_solution.csv is used. 1% of the rows are selected (about 5447 images) for the lower layers. 32 random patches are selected for each image. LOC_val_solution.csv is used as test data.
- Then, for each patch, the label is the corresponding class of the image. But, given that there are 1000 classes, it is split into 5 sub-classes, 2-bits each. This is to make sure XGBoost doesn't have to predict 1000 classes at once, but, 5 XGBoost models can predict 2-bits each independently.
- Then, it is supposed to be resized by 2x2 (i.e., 128x128, 64x64 etc.) using mode of those four "sub-class pixels".
- One metric that should be used is LSNR (Log Signal to Noise Ratio). $\log(\frac{Signal}{Noise+1})$ The Signal is the number of class pixels which are the same as that of the training class or testing class. Noise are the remaining ones.
- 16-bit integer is the data-type that is used.

Figure 1: Initial layer will have to do with prediction of sub-class for each 5x5 patch. Then, the 5 channel sub-class image is resized. This is supposed to be done recursively.[2]

4 Explainable ML

The main idea is to use "and" logic to explain consistent "correct class" predictions. As we are considering layers which have different shapes (given that they are like image pyramids), we need to do "and" logic between layers (from the upper layers of course (may be which are smaller than 64x64)) only after we have resized all layers to be 256x256. Resize has to be done by repeating though.

5 Joint Probability models

The idea is to "generate" the upper layers using six 4-bit nibble predictions for H, S, V channels when we have lower resolution image and we need to predict the upper resolution image; the lower resolution image will have to be resized to the upper resolution shape using interpolation and trained using lower resolution image once and predictions of the lower layer the second time. The image inverse pyramid scale is two for each layer.

5.1 Position information

For generative model, both X and Y coordinates should help. For discriminative model, this is not needed. However, the experiments of this paper do not use position information.

Figure 2: The left image is about the functional convolution-like operation. The right image is about the actual resized image XGBoost model predicting the 4-bit nibbles: upper H nibble, lower H nibble, upper S nibble, lower S nibble, upper V nibble, lower V nibble. This is to be repeated for different resolutions to get the desired inverted image pyramid.

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